

New long-acting [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO GLP-1 PET tracers with increased molar activity and reduced kidney accumulation

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Abstract

Positron emission tomography (PET) imaging is used in drug development to non-invasively measure biodistribution and receptor occupancy. Ideally, PET tracers retain target binding and biodistribution properties of the investigated drug. Previously, we developed a zirconium-89 PET tracer based on a long-circulating glucagon-like peptide 1 receptor agonist (GLP-1RA) using desferrioxamine (DFO) as chelator. Here, we aimed to develop an improved zirconium-89-labeled GLP-1RA with increased molar activity to increase the uptake in low receptor density tissues, such as brain. Furthermore, we aimed at reducing tracer accumulation in kidneys. Introducing up to four additional Zr-DFOs resulted in higher molar activity and stability, while retaining potency. Branched placement of DFOs was especially beneficial. Tracers with either two or four DFOs had similar biodistribution as the tracer with one DFO in vivo, albeit increased kidney and liver uptake. Reduced kidney accumulation was achieved by introducing an enzymatically cleavable MVK linker motif between chelator and peptide.

Introduction

Modern drug development often necessitates careful assessment of specific tissue targeting, receptor occupancy and biodistribution. Molecular imaging technologies provide a tool for early evaluation of drug candidates and is utilized in several stages of drug development¹. During safety assessment, biodistribution is usually evaluated using ³H or ¹⁴C-tracers in quantitative whole body autoradiography (QWBA)². Biodistribution data from QWBA studies is widely accepted by regulatory authorities but the technique is invasive and lacks translatability from preclinical species to humans. Early access to human data provides the best translational value and is strongly desired within the pharmaceutical industry.^{3, 4} Positron emission tomography (PET) imaging offers the possibility to generate human data non-invasively⁵, therefore PET imaging is an attractive technology for drug development.^{6, 7} It has been used in pre-clinical and clinical settings, to assess biodistribution⁸⁻¹⁴, receptor occupancy¹⁵⁻¹⁷ target engagement^{1, 18} and tissue targeting.¹⁹⁻²² PET requires labelling of the drug molecule with a positron emitting radionuclide for detection. For imaging of long-acting molecules such as antibodies or protracted peptides (half-life extended e.g. via albumin binding by a conjugated fatty (di)acid), zirconium-89 (⁸⁹Zr]Zr) is an attractive radionuclide, due to its long half-life (78 h).²³ Drug molecules are usually labelled with [⁸⁹Zr]Zr by conjugation to desferrioxamine (DFO) which chelates the radiometal.

However, there are several challenges when using PET in drug development. Labelling of the drug molecule (e.g. attachment of a chelator) should not alter pharmacokinetics (PK) and the uptake route should be via the same mechanism as the parent compound (e.g. for receptor mediated uptake). It is also desirable to retain the pharmacodynamic effect of the parent molecule, as this can be used as a positive indicator for a similar structure, receptor binding, tissue distribution and mode of uptake compared to the drug candidate, although also receptor antagonists can be used for PET imaging. Moreover, assessing receptor occupancy in areas with low receptor density can be challenging, requiring high molar activity (A_m) of the tracer. Finally, kidney accumulation, via megalin-mediated proximal tubular reabsorption²⁴, is a well-known phenomenon especially of peptide-based PET tracers labelled with radiometals.²⁵ This can render false results in biodistribution studies as well as limit clinical use due to nephrotoxicity when using therapeutic radionuclides.

We have previously developed a protracted glucagon-like peptide 1 receptor agonist (GLP-1RA) PET tracer, applying [⁸⁹Zr]Zr as the long-acting PET isotope.²⁶ The PET tracer was found to have biological half-life comparable to clinically approved semaglutide (ca 10 h in rats) and similar biodistribution as a QWBA tracer.²⁷ Long-acting GLP-1RAs, such as semaglutide and dulaglutide are used clinically to treat type 2 diabetes and semaglutide has recently been approved to treat obesity. Pharmacological treatment with GLP-1RA potentiates glucose-dependent insulin secretion and leads to weight loss mainly due to a reduction in energy intake.^{28, 29} The weight loss is likely resulting from the action of subcutaneously administered GLP-1RA peptides within the central nervous system (CNS).³⁰ This is potentially also the case for several other peptide-based agonists currently in development targeting other receptors.³¹⁻³⁴ Therefore, the possibility of imaging target engagement and distribution within the brain in a translatable fashion (e.g. with PET) is highly desirable. However, in our previous study, no distribution to the brain of the GLP-1RA PET tracer was observed with PET.²⁷ This is most likely explained by the fact that a mixture of PET ligand and unlabelled drug compound was administered, to mimic what is traditionally done in QWBA studies, which however limits the visualization of target engagement, especially in low receptor expressing tissues. A tracer with higher A_m is likely necessary in imaging target engagement within the brain. A further limitation of the forementioned GLP-1 PET tracer was the high kidney uptake, which resulted in a mismatch between PET and QWBA biodistributions. A promising approach to reduce kidney accumulation is to

introduce a cleavable linker between the peptide and the radionuclide, which would allow the latter to be released in the urine.²⁵ Cleavage is mediated by the enzyme neutral endopeptidase (NEP), which is highly expressed on renal brush border membrane (BBM). The strategy has been utilized for various peptide-based PET tracers, including GLP-1, and chelators applying different di- or tripeptide linkers.³⁵⁻⁴²

In this work, we aim at developing 2nd generation [⁸⁹Zr]Zr based GLP-1 PET tracers which are suitable for imaging receptor uptake in brain and other low receptor density tissues. Furthermore, we aim to reduce kidney uptake to develop tracers which show a more representative biodistribution similar to QWBA tracers. Previously, increased A_m of an unprotracted GLP-1 PET tracer was achieved by addition of multiple lysine residues with attached DTPA chelators (Figure 1A) to the C-terminal.⁴³ For reducing kidney uptake, the enzymatically cleavable Met-Val-Lys (MVK) motif has been particularly successful for various peptide-based PET tracers (Figure 1B).^{35, 37, 38, 40} Inspired by these studies, we first evaluated strategies to attach up to four DFO chelators to our model protracted GLP-1RA, aiming to increase A_m without compromising potency (Figure 1C). In a separate tracer, we introduced the MVK linker between the chelator and the peptide (Figure 1D). Radiolabelling efficiency as well as stability of the multi-chelator peptides were determined, and finally PET imaging and biodistribution studies were performed for the newly developed [⁸⁹Zr]Zr based GLP-1 PET tracers. For the multichelated peptides, the molar activity was deliberately reduced to match the previously reported doses, for determining how the introduction of additional DFO motifs influence the tracer biodistribution.

Figure 1. Upper panel: previously reported methods for increasing specific activity (A) and reducing kidney uptake (B) of peptide and protein-based SPECT tracers. Lower panel: new strategy for increasing specific activity (C) by linear or dendrimer DFO expansion and reducing kidney uptake (D) of long-acting GLP-1 receptor agonist [^{89}Zr]Zr PET tracer.

Results

Design, synthesis and in vitro potency evaluation of new GLP-1 PET tracer molecules with improved properties

With the purpose of developing PET tracers based on parent GLP-1RA **1** with increased molar activity, we initially designed new tracers having two DFO chelators (Figure 2A, upper panel). We opted to again use the DFO-Sq chelator to allow comparison with previous published data, and for advantages in stability and handling.²⁶ The previously developed PET tracer **2**²⁶ was either expanded in the C-terminal with lysine residues bearing DFO chelators (**3** and **4**) or modified with a second DFO or the fatty diacid protractor (**5**, **6** and **7**) on a lysine residue in position 34 (native GLP-1). Previous structure-activity-relationship data

The set of peptides containing 2 DFO was tested for in vitro activity on the GLP-1 receptor, both with empty and occupied chelators (non-radioactive Zr), in a screening setup including receptor binding and potency assays. Either 0% or 1% of human serum albumin (HSA) in the assay buffer was used, the presence of HSA lowers the apparent potency giving an indirect measurement of the albumin binding properties of the analogue.⁴⁴ A larger loss in the potency in the presence of albumin indicates stronger albumin binding, which in turn could result in longer PK. Results from the potency assays are indicated in Table 1 as a factor loss vs **1** and correlated well to the binding assay (data not shown). Peptides bearing both chelators at the C-terminal (**3**, **4** and **5**) showed only a moderate 4-6-fold loss of potency. Introducing the extra chelator at Lys34 resulted in somewhat larger losses (**6** and **7**), whereas the protractor was better tolerated in this position (**5**). Chelators in positions 16 and 22 in general resulted in substantially reduced potency. The branched lysine structure at the C-terminal resulted in the lowest loss of potency, and when chelated with zirconium, **13** behaved virtually identical to **1**.

Encouraged by the retained potency of GLP-1RA bearing two DFO chelators, we synthesized peptides with 3 or 4 DFO (Figure 2A, lower panel). Here, C-terminal expansion with Gly-Gly-Ser linkers and moving the protractor to Lys34 were the main strategies (**14**, **15**, **16** and **17**). A lysine dendrimer with 4 DFO was also made (**18**). In this case, the branched structure was achieved by a different orthogonal protection strategy. Wang resin was loaded with Alloc-Lys(Fmoc)-OH, then branched on the lysine sidechain via Fmoc-Lys(Fmoc)-OH, and finally further branched with two Boc-Lys(Boc)-OH (Figure 2B, lower panel). The main peptide sequence was continued after Alloc removal. Although the GLP-1RA bearing multiple DFO were synthesized with reasonable efficiency, their analysis by UPLC-UV or MS deemed somewhat challenging (Supplementary information). Peak separation on longer gradients was observed, likely due to incorporation or release of metals into/from the DFO chelators. Peptides from the second set were in general slightly less potent than the corresponding peptide with two DFO (**4** and **5**). It was noted that it seemed beneficial to move the protractor to lys34 (**14** vs **16** and **15** vs **17**). This effect was most pronounced when chelated to Zr. The lysine dendrimer with 4 DFO (**18**) reduced the potency by an order of magnitude without zirconium, but only gave a loss of 3.8-fold when fully chelated. The lysine branching strategy hence gave the most potent tracer containing 4 DFO, in line with the observation for the peptides containing 2 DFO. Finally, a peptide was synthesized in which the C-terminal was expanded with the enzymatically cleavable linker motif MVK (**19**). The DFO chelator was attached to the lysine in the MVK motif. This tracer was essentially equipotent to **1**.

To rationalize how the DFO chelators may influence GLP-1R binding, a 3D model of peptide **18** was generated (Figure 3). For the 4xSq-DFO-Zr dendrimer lysine conjugation, a particular effort was made to approximate 7 coordinate complexes involving DFO's three bidentate hydroxamate groups and one dione squareamide oxygen per Zr⁴⁺ metal ion, as previously proposed by quantum mechanics calculations.⁴⁵ This feasible configuration of the PET tracer bound to the GLP-1R highlights two main findings i) peptide-receptor interactions are retained relative to parent peptides, and ii) DFO and protractor groups are able to explore bulk solvent areas separated from the membrane, without engaging in significant clashes nor interactions with the receptor. This in agreement with the limited 3.8-fold loss in potency of **18** relative to **1** in the presence of Zr (Table 1).

Figure 3. 3D model of peptide **18**. A 3D model of peptide **18** is aligned to semaglutide as solved bound to the GLP-1R by Cryo-EM (PDB ID 7KI0).⁴⁶ The peptide is represented in van der Waals radius spheres and color-coded according to Figure 1C, with peptide backbone and fatty acid in blue, Gly-Gly-Ser linker in green, dendrimer chelators in orange and Zr atoms shown in cyan. The GLP-1R is displayed in white and has labels for relevant transmembrane helices. The two horizontal dotted planes represent the borders of the hydrocarbon core of a (cellular membrane) lipid bilayer as predicted by the OPM database⁴⁷

Evaluation of maximal labelling efficiency and in vitro stability

A set of peptides, with different numbers of DFO, having the best properties in terms of GLP-1 potency were selected for radiolabelling studies. Peptides **4**, **5** and **13** bearing two DFO, **16** with three DFO and **17** and **18** with four DFO were selected. To assess whether additional DFO chelators increase the molar activity (A_m) of the GLP-1RA PET tracers, the selected peptides were radiolabelled with different amounts of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr and compared to **2** having one DFO (Figure 4A and Table S2). Molar activity and labelling efficiency were determined by instant thin-layer chromatography (iTLC) analysis. Labelling efficiency is defined as the fraction of the utilized [⁸⁹Zr]Zr which is chelated to the peptide via DFO. In general, 10-15% increase in A_m was observed when increasing the amount of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr from 20 MBq to 30 MBq per nmol of peptide. For those amounts of radioactivity, **2**, **4** and **5** showed low labelling efficiency (ca 40%), indicating saturation of the DFO chelators. In contrast, **13**, **16**, **17** and **18** showed higher values for the radiolabelling efficiency (70-80%), indicating remaining capacity of the DFOs to coordinate more [⁸⁹Zr]Zr. The increase in A_m was also larger for **18** (47%). We therefore labelled the most promising dendrimer like tracers **13** and **18** with larger amounts of radioactivity, namely 60 MBq and 120 MBq [⁸⁹Zr]Zr per nmol peptide respectively. In this experiment the A_m was increased substantially, reaching 55 MBq/nmol for **13** and 84 MBq/nmol for **18**. Peptide **13** had a very high labelling efficiency, therefore even higher A_m can likely be reached for this tracer.

Figure 4. A) Radiolabelling of peptides containing multiple DFO chelators using varying amounts of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr per nmol of peptide. The colour denotes the amount of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr used for the radiolabelling. Left panel shows the achieved molar activity (A_m) of the tracer immediately after labelling (individual values as circles). The right panel shows the labelling efficiency (individual values as dots, average values as horizontal bar and standard deviation). B) Stability of peptides radiolabelled with 20 MBq [⁸⁹Zr]Zr per nmol peptide after 1 week incubation in phosphate buffered saline (left), fetal calf serum (middle) and with 1000 equiv EDTA (right). The percentage of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr remaining chelated to the peptide is indicated on the y-axis. C) Stability of peptides radiolabelled with 30 MBq [⁸⁹Zr]Zr per nmol peptide (left) and 60 MBq (peptide **13**) or 120 MBq (peptide **18**) [⁸⁹Zr]Zr per nmol peptide (right) after 1 week incubation in phosphate buffered saline with 1000 equiv EDTA. The percentage of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr remaining chelated to the peptide is indicated on the y-axis. The number of replicates varies from 1-3 for the different peptides and experiments and are found in tables S2, S3, S4 and S5 in the supplementary information, where all individual values are presented.

The ability of the selected tracers to retain the ^{89}Zr Zr coordinated to the DFO was determined in stability studies. The tracers were incubated up to 1 week in either phosphate buffered saline (PBS), fetal calf serum (FCS) or PBS with 1000 equivalents of Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) and the amount ^{89}Zr Zr chelated to the peptide was determined by iTLC (Figure 4B and Table S3). When incubating the tracers produced using 20 MBq ^{89}Zr Zr per nmol peptide, it was observed that **2**, **4** and **5**, having one or two DFO, had remarkably lower stability. Peptides **2** and **5** chelated less than 50% of the ^{89}Zr Zr, when incubated in PBS at the earliest time point (1 h). In contrast, peptides having either two DFO in dendrimer structure (**13**) or three (**16**) and four DFO (**17** and **18**) retained ca 50% of the ^{89}Zr Zr after 168 h under the same conditions. The order was the same when incubated in FCS and EDTA, however the effect was less and more pronounced respectively. The large difference in stability between **4/5** and **13**, all bearing two DFO, was attributed to stabilizing effects of the dendrimer structure. Peptide **19**, also containing one DFO, showed similar results to **2**, **4** and **5**. When the tracers were produced using more ^{89}Zr Zr, to have higher A_m , the results were similar (Figure 4C). Peptides **13** and **18** produced with 60 and 120 MBq ^{89}Zr Zr per nmol peptide were more stable than with the lower A_m . The cause of this phenomenon is unclear but taken together the results highlight the superior stability of the dendrimer like chelators.

PET study using multichelated tracer

Based on the potency and stability results, peptides **13** and **18** were selected for PET and ex vivo biodistribution studies. Although higher A_m were possible, the dose was normalised with cold peptide to be comparable to the previous study of **2**.²⁷ Similar to ^{89}Zr Zr-**2**, the PET images of ^{89}Zr Zr-**13** and ^{89}Zr Zr-**18** showed high uptake of the tracers in kidneys, lungs, liver, intestine and urinary tract (Figure 5A). At the 4 h time point, the vascular system could be clearly visualized in the upper body of the animal, with strong signal from the heart and carotid arteries. At the 24 h time point, the tracers localize further to the kidneys as well as to liver and bones. No uptake was observed in the brain at any time point. The ex vivo biodistribution at 24 h of ^{89}Zr Zr-**13** was very similar to ^{89}Zr Zr-**2**, both tracers correlating reasonably well with ^3H]2 QWBA biodistribution, with exception of kidney uptake (Figure 5B). A similar distribution was observed for ^{89}Zr Zr-**18**, however, with markedly increased distribution to especially kidney but also liver and bone marrow. The ex vivo data correlated well with the in vivo images, and no brain uptake could be detected for any of the tracers.

A

B

Figure 5. A) in vivo positron emission tomography (PET) images showing the biodistribution of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr labelled peptide **13** and peptide **18** at 4 and 24 hours after intravenous injection. Dorsal (left), and sagittal (middle) view of upper body and dorsal view of lower body (right) The upper and lower body were captured in separate bed-positions and therefore not depicted as a single image. Representative images are shown from each group at each time point for comparison. Rats were injected with 16-24 MBq (4 nmol) / kg of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-labelled peptides. Data is expressed as the percentage of the injected dose per gram (%ID/g). B) Ex-vivo biodistribution by gamma counting in selected tissues after dosing with [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-**2**, [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-**13** and [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-**18** at 24 hours after intravenous injection. Bar graphs data is shown as mean \pm SD, n=5, circles indicate the individual data points. Ex vivo biodistribution by QWBA of [³H]**2** is shown as reference. Data is expressed as the percentage of the injected dose per gram (%ID/g). Data for [³H]**2** and [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-**2** are from the previous study.²⁷

PET study using cleavable MVK-linker

Peptide **19** was found to have similar potency and stability properties as **2** and was hence evaluated in PET biodistribution. The in vivo PET images showed that [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-**19** distributes like the other tested PET tracers, with high uptake in kidneys, lungs, liver, intestine and urinary tract (Figure 6A). The signal from the kidneys increased over time. However, the kidney uptake of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-**19** was substantially reduced when compared to [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-**2**.²⁷ Notably, at early time points, heart and blood vessels were more distinguishable and liver uptake was somewhat higher. The ex vivo biodistribution correlated well with in vivo PET images, and it was observed that [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-**19** had approximately half the kidney uptake of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-**2**, (signal reduced from 8.3 to 4.8 %ID/g at 24 h, p = 0.00006) but not as low as [³H]**2** assessed by QWBA (2.2% ID/g) (Figure 6B and Tables S6, S7, S10, S11). However, at 24 h liver uptake of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-**19** was somewhat higher than for [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-**2**. As observed previously for [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-**2**, at 72 h significant signal from the [⁸⁹Zr]Zr tracers remained in lung, liver and kidneys, whereas the [³H] signal was observed only in minuscule amounts.

A

B

Figure 6. A) Dorsal view in vivo positron emission tomography (PET) images showing the biodistribution of $[^{89}\text{Zr}]$ Zr labelled peptide **19**, containing a cleavable MVK linker, and peptide **2** at 4, 8, 24 and 72 hours after intravenous injection. Representative images are shown from each group at each time point for comparison. Rats were injected with 20 MBq (4 nmol) / kg of $[^{89}\text{Zr}]$ Zr-labelled peptides. Data is expressed as the percentage of the injected dose per gram (%ID/g). B) Ex-vivo biodistribution by gamma counting in selected tissues after dosing with $[^{89}\text{Zr}]$ Zr-**19** and $[^{89}\text{Zr}]$ Zr-**2** at 24 and 72 hours after intravenous injection. Bar graphs data is shown as mean \pm SD, n=5, circles indicate the individual data points. Ex vivo biodistribution by QWBA of $[^3\text{H}]2$ is shown as reference. Data is expressed as the percentage of the injected dose per gram (%ID/g). Data for $[^3\text{H}]2$ and $[^{89}\text{Zr}]$ Zr-**2** are from the previous study.²⁷

Discussion

PET is a promising technology for generating early human data in drug development. Monitoring biodistribution and receptor occupancy by PET in various tissues is highly desirable but remains a challenge, especially in tissues with low receptor density. Several peptide-based modalities, including protracted GLP-1RAs are likely mediating their actions at least partly in the brain and hence monitoring of their activity in the brain is highly desirable. The GLP-1R is distributed in neurons in several distinct areas in rodent, primate, and human brain, mainly in regions which regulate feeding.^{48, 49} It has been demonstrated that fluorescently- or radio-labelled GLP-1RAs reach these areas upon systemic administration.⁵⁰⁻⁵² Notably, semaglutide did not cross the blood-brain barrier but interacted with the brain through the circumventricular organs. PET imaging has also been used with GLP-1R binding peptides, e.g. for imaging malign insulinomas^{53, 54} or beta cell mass, usually with short half-life variants without albumin-binding protractors.⁵⁵⁻⁵⁷ No brain uptake has been detected using this technology. We hypothesize that the lack of results could be related to suboptimal properties of the PET tracers, among others low A_m . Furthermore, for evaluating biodistribution, PET of peptide-based ligands conjugated to a chelator with a radiometal tends to severely overestimate kidney uptake. In this work, we sought to develop improved versions of a [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO-GLP-1RA PET tracer, which would be suitable for brain imaging or give a more representative biodistribution.

When developing such tracer molecules, retained receptor binding is important. We demonstrate here that when attaching the chelator in certain positions, GLP-1R *in vitro* potency is preserved, even when as many as four DFO are attached to the peptide. Modelling of peptide **18**, having four DFO in a dendrimer structure, showed that the chelators can face the solvent-exposed extracellular environment, without interfering with the receptor. In general, peptides with an occupied chelator were more potent, hence we would advocate for such testing of newly developed tracer molecules. This observation could be rationalized by the fact that, when unchelated, the highly flexible DFO moiety may impair receptor binding sterically or due to an entropic penalty effect or negative electronic effects. The 3D model of peptide **18** suggests that the addition of Zr could indeed minimize the entropic penalty upon binding by reducing DFO disorder. This way the dendrimer would retain a more compact conformation which could possibly increase the population of conformations that are competent for receptor binding. Interestingly, the DFO dendrimer structures were most potent. In a recent study, the A_m of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-trastuzumab was increased by randomly attaching up to 10 DFO.⁵⁸ This led to decreased target binding and *in vivo* performance, the authors speculating that dendrimer chelators could mitigate this problem. Indeed, our results support this hypothesis, even for a moiety which is ca 30-fold smaller than trastuzumab and which would therefore theoretically be more compromised by the size of the extra DFO.

In line with this study, we demonstrate that the A_m of the GLP-1 PET tracers could be amplified by increasing number of DFOs. The theoretical A_m of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr when provided from the cyclotron is approximately 26 MBq/nmol⁵⁹ but may vary depending on the time of delivery. Labelling the tracers with 20-30 MBq [⁸⁹Zr]Zr per nmol peptide theoretically corresponds to saturating 1 DFO chelator. Our results point at saturation of the tracers with 1 or 2 DFOs under such conditions, as shown by the decrease in labelling efficiency. However, to fully explore the potential of increased A_m we increased the amount of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr and used it as close to production as practically possible. In this experiment, A_m close to the theoretical maximum values of the dendrimer DFO tracers were observed. Our measured A_m of 83.6 MBq/nmol is the largest reported to date for a ⁸⁹Zr-DFO-GLP-1RA PET tracer and is well in line with the value of 175 MBq/nmol of trastuzumab bearing 10.9 DFO on average.⁵⁸

Stability of PET tracers is an important property, especially when using radionuclides with long half-life, such as [⁸⁹Zr]Zr. DFO, the commonly used chelator for [⁸⁹Zr]Zr, is suboptimal as a fraction of the [⁸⁹Zr]Zr is released in vivo. Much effort has been going into developing more stable DFO based chelators for [⁸⁹Zr]Zr, including the somewhat stabilizing squaramide ester.⁶⁰ Our results indicate that the branched lysine structure provided the best stability among peptides with two DFO, whereas the effect was not clear with four DFO. In general, increased number of DFO resulted in better stability. We hypothesize that this effect is due to empty DFO chelators in proximity, which would either “catch” released [⁸⁹Zr]Zr or the [⁸⁹Zr]Zr being coordinated by multiple DFO, as recently observed in another study.⁶¹ Hence, if tolerated by the investigated drug, attaching multiple DFO, preferably in a dendrimer fashion, could be an alternative approach to improve the stability of PET tracers. Notably, **2** and **4** showed the lowest stability which was lower than previously obtained for **2**. This could be explained by the radiolabelling procedure, where in the present study **2** was radiolabelled at >4 times higher radioactivity per nmol than previously. This resulted in a higher specific activity, but also a lower stability. Peptide **4**, having only one DFO as well showed a similar behaviour, confirming that high molar activity may result in lower stability.

When examined in vivo, we opted to adjust the dose of the high A_m tracers [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-**13** and [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-**18**, to allow comparison of biodistribution to [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-**2**. The biodistribution of the compared tracers was indeed similar, indicating that even four DFOs do not substantially influence distribution of the GLP1-RA within this timeframe (72 h). However, kidney and liver uptake increased when increasing the number of DFOs. This is undesired in biodistribution studies but considered acceptable if monitoring receptor uptake, which was the purpose of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-**13** and [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-**18**. It should be mentioned that albumin bound tracers of this type have a long retention time in the body, which could potentially cause prolonged exposure to radioactivity. Despite using tracers with higher A_m, no brain uptake was observed in vivo or ex vivo. This is potentially explained by the forementioned dose adjustment, where unlabelled peptide was added. Brain receptors are possibly saturated with peptides not bearing [⁸⁹Zr]Zr, and hence no uptake is detected. Another possibility is that modification of the GLP-1RA with DFO chelators negatively influences passage into GLP-1 receptor containing areas in the brain. Further, in rodents the resolution of the PET system could limit brain detection. Notably, in a recent clinical study of an unprotracted GLP-1RA PET tracer (exendin-4-⁶⁸Ga-NODAGA), no brain uptake was observed either.⁶² However, the authors mention several limitations of the study, such as the small number of subjects, the timing of the PET imaging and the possibility of radionuclide labelling affecting access to brain areas. The necessity of replication is pointed out, indicating further interest and possibilities within this field.

For developing a GLP-1 PET tracer with reduced renal uptake, an enzymatically cleavable linker was introduced between the chelator and the peptide, being more convenient as compared to other strategies.⁶³ Co-injection of various agents such as fructose⁶⁴, basic amino acids⁶⁵, albumin fragments⁶⁶ or a gelatin-based plasma expander^{67,68} have all shown to reduce kidney entrapment of peptide and protein-based PET tracers. Modifying the tracer with an albumin binding moiety⁶⁹ or adding negative charges⁷⁰ also reduce kidney uptake. Enzymatically cleavable peptide-based linkers have been used clinically to reduce radioactive exposure in undesired tissues.⁷¹ The MVK linker motif was chosen based on previous characterisation. Other linkers, such as meprin β-specific cleavable linkers have also been evaluated, albeit with less success than the MVK.⁷² We demonstrate here that the tracer containing the MVK linker has suitable in vitro properties, and results in a substantially reduced kidney uptake. To our knowledge, this is the first time DFO is utilized as a chelator with this approach. Our study shows that it is possible to use long-acting isotopes such as [⁸⁹Zr]Zr with reduced kidney uptake, which is desirable when nephrotoxicity could be an issue. Moreover, the strategy gives more representative biodistribution values, which approach those obtained by QWBA. QWBA is regarded as giving the best approximation of biodistribution, due to the

minimal alteration of the parent molecule. It is noted that our strategy for reducing kidney uptake can likely be combined with the dendrimer chelators to minimize the kidney uptake of the latter. One limitation of utilizing a linker which is cleavable by NEP is that while the protease is primarily expressed on cell membrane anchored in kidneys, it is also present in other tissues such as brain and lungs, and even in blood plasma in soluble form.⁷³ This could result in premature cleavage of the chelator containing the radiometal and hence either off-target accumulation or false biodistribution. In our study, we observed slightly higher liver uptake of the tracer containing the MVK linker motif, which could potentially be explained by undesired NEP cleavage. No other tissue accumulation was detected, and we point out that the main effect of MVK linker inclusion was the reduced kidney uptake.

Conclusion

In this work, strategies to increase the A_m and reduce the kidney uptake of protracted DFO- ^{89}Zr Zr GLP-1RA PET tracers were evaluated. Radiotracers with high A_m (up to 83.6 MBq/nmol) were achieved by increasing the number of DFO chelators to two or four. Chelator position and linker strategy influenced receptor potency and in vitro radio-stability; the most optimal tracers, also with highest A_m , were conjugated at the C-terminal via a dendrimer structure. PET imaging of two selected dendrimer tracers (two or four DFOs) overall showed a similar biodistribution as the previously tested monochelated tracer, although kidney and liver uptake increased. Such change in distribution to the excretory organs needs to be considered for a biodistribution study but may be insignificant for imaging of other and selected target tissues. In the selected study design, no signal was detected in the brain, likely due to saturation of receptors by unlabelled peptide.

Further, the introduction of a cleavable MVK linker motif between chelator and peptide successfully reduced kidney accumulation of a DFO- ^{89}Zr Zr GLP-1RA PET tracer (1.7-fold reduction at 24 h). As a result, PET biodistribution values more closely resembled those obtained by gold standard QWBA imaging.

In summary, our results indicate that arranging multiple DFOs in a dendrimer fashion is a promising approach to both enhance the A_m and improve radio-stability of ^{89}Zr -PET tracers. The MVK linker motif can be readily applied, orthogonally to other approaches, to reduce kidney accumulation. Finally, we believe that the strategies developed in this work can be generally utilized on radiotracers which require high A_m and radio-stability and where low kidney accumulation is desired.

Experimental

General peptide synthesis

Solid-phase peptide synthesis was performed on a SymphonyX automated synthesizer (Gyros Protein Technologies) or a Liberty Blue microwave peptide synthesizer (CEM) using standard Fmoc protocols. Wang resin pre-loaded with the C-terminal amino acid was used as solid support. On SymphonyX, peptide couplings were carried out by reacting amino acid (4 equiv) with OxymaPure (4 equiv) and DIC (4 equiv) in DMF. N-terminal Fmoc protecting groups were removed using 20% piperidine in DMF. On Liberty blue, 5 equiv amino acid, 5 equiv OxymaPure and 5 equiv DIC were used in the peptide couplings at 75 °C. Fmoc de-protection was performed with 5% piperidine in DMF at 75 °C. Fmoc-Lys(Mtt) was used for selective incorporation of the fatty acid side chain. After assembly of the complete peptide sequence, the Mtt side chain protecting group was selectively deprotected by treatment with HFIP/TIPS/DCM (75:2.5:22.5) for 30 min. The free amine was then reacted with the succinimidyl-ester of the fatty-acid side chain (6 equiv) using DIPEA (10 equiv) in DMF. Final deprotection and cleavage from the resin were done in a cleavage cocktail containing TFA/water/TIPS (95/2.5/2.5) for 1.5 h. The resin was removed by filtration and peptides precipitated in ice-cold diethyl ether. The precipitate was pelleted by centrifugation and washed twice with diethyl ether. Peptides were purified using a RP-HPLC system equipped with a preparative C18 column (Phenomenex Gemini 5 μm NX C18 110Å, 30 x 250 mm). Different preparative HPLC gradients were used depending on the hydrophobicity of the peptides, a general method consisted of a linear gradient of 35–60% solvent B (MeCN, 0.1% [v/v] TFA) in solvent A (H₂O, 0.1% [v/v] TFA) over 30 minutes at a flow rate of 20 ml min⁻¹. Fractions containing the desired compound were pooled and lyophilized to yield the peptides as fluffy, white powders. All compounds were analysed by C18 RP-UPLC-UV and RP-LCMS, using various methods (Supplementary information). The purity of the compounds was in general 90-100%. Using these methods, peptides bearing multiple DFO often show slight peak separation on longer analytical gradients likely related to the incorporation or release of metal ions to/from the chelators.

DFO conjugation

The conjugation of one or several DFO chelators to the peptide was performed using a purified peptide precursor containing unprotected lysine residues. The peptide was dissolved in sodium bicarbonate buffer (0.1 M, pH 11) and MeCN (20%). DFO squaramide ester (DFOSqOEt) was prepared from 3,4-diethoxy-3-cyclobutene-1,2-dione and deferoxamine mesylate salt as previously described.²⁶ Two equivalents of DFOSqOEt per free lysine residue were added and the reaction stirred over night at 50 °C. The reaction was either quenched with acetic acid and purified as above or taken directly for non-radioactive zirconium chelation.

Non-radioactive zirconium chelation

The reaction mix from DFO conjugation (as described above) was diluted with sodium bicarbonate buffer and the pH adjusted to 9. Aqueous ZrCl₄ (4 equiv per DFO) was added to the reaction mix. Full chelation was usually observed within 5 min. The desired product was purified by RP-HPLC as described above. In cases where a purified peptide precursor was used for zirconium chelation, removal of excess zirconium after chelation was performed using a Zeba spin desalting column with 7K MWCO (Thermo Scientific).

Synthesis of DFO dendrimer peptides

Peptide 13 2 DFO dendrimer: The tetra peptide Fmoc-GGSK(Mtt) was synthesized on the Liberty Blue peptide synthesizer using pre-loaded Lys(Mtt) Wang resin and conditions as described above, without final de-protection, hence leaving the N-terminal Fmoc protecting group intact. The Mtt protecting group on the C-terminal lysine residue was selectively de-protected using TFA/TIPS/DCM (1:2:97) for 30 min. The presence of the Fmoc protecting group on the N-terminus was confirmed by LCMS analysis. Then Boc-

Lys(Boc)-OH was coupled onto the free amine on the C-terminal lysine residue, and synthesis of the full peptide backbone, including fatty acid side chain coupling, continued as described above, after removal of the N-terminal Fmoc protecting group. The DFO conjugation was performed as described above, but 4 equivalents of DFOSqOEt per free amine were required to achieve full conversion to the desired product. Non-radioactive zirconium chelation was performed as above.

Peptide 18 4 DFO dendrimer: Wang resin was manually loaded with Alloc-Lys(Fmoc)-OH by incubation of the resin with amino acid (4 equiv), OxymaPure (4 equiv), DIC (4 equiv) and DMAP (0.1 equiv) in DCM for 3 h shaking at room temperature. The remaining reactive groups on the resin were capped using acetic anhydride (5%) and DIPEA (2 equiv) in DMF. Loading was confirmed by Fmoc test cleavage with 20% piperidine in DMF followed by absorbance measurement at 290 and 301 nm. The lysine dendrimer was synthesized on the Liberty Blue synthesizer by coupling Fmoc-Lys(Fmoc)-OH onto the side chain amine of the resin anchored lysine followed by coupling Boc-Lys(Boc)-OH onto both amines of the second lysine. The N-terminal alloc protecting group on the resin anchored lysine was subsequently de-protected by treatment with Pd(PPh₃)₄ (0.05 equiv in degassed DCM) and BH₃NH(CH₃)₂ (15 equiv in degassed DCM) under nitrogen atmosphere for 1 h. Synthesis of the full peptide backbone, including fatty acid side chain coupling, then continued as described above. The DFO conjugation was performed as described above, but 4 equivalents of DFOSqOEt per free amine were required to achieve full conversion to the desired product. Non-radioactive zirconium chelation was performed as above.

In vitro GLP-1R potency assay

Cyclic AMP (cAMP) potency was measured using a clonal BHK cell line co-expressing the human GLP-1R and the cAMP response element (CRE) luciferase reporter gene. On the day of the assay, frozen cells stocks of assay-ready cells were thawed in a 37 °C water bath, washed once in PBS (Gibco, 14190-094) and diluted to 100.000 cells/ml in assay buffer without or with 2% (w/v) HSA (Sigma, A9511). The assay buffer consisted of DMEM without phenol red (Gibco, 11880-028) supplemented with 1X GlutaMAX (Gibco, 35050-038), 10 mM HEPES (Gibco, 15630-056), 1% (w/v) ovalbumin (Sigma, A5503) and 0.1% (v/v) Pluronic F-68 (Gibco, 24040-032). Serial dilutions (10-fold dilutions, 8 concentrations pr. compound) were performed in assay buffer without HSA in a 96-well dilution plate (Greiner Bio-one, U-shape, 650201) using a Biomek i7 liquid handler (Beckman-Coulter). From the dilution plate, 50 µl of each dilution was transferred to two 96-well assay plates (ThermoFisher, 237105) to which 50 µl of the cell suspension either with or without 2% (w/v) HSA was added (5.000 cells/well). The assay plates were incubated for 3 hours at 37 °C in 5% CO₂, left at room temperature for 5 minutes after which 100 µl SteadyLite Plus (PerkinElmer, 6066759) was added to each well (final concentration of HSA was 0 or 1%). Plates were sealed and incubated at room temperature with gentle shaking for 30 minutes while protected from light. Luminescence was detected on a Synergy 2 (BioTek) luminescence plate reader and the EC₅₀-values calculated by non-linear curve fitting using a four-parameter logistic model (Hill slope = 1) using GraphPad Prism or by means of TIBCO Enterprise Runtime for R (TIBCO Software, Palo Alto, CA, USA).

Animals

Experiments involving animals in this study were approved by the Dutch central committee on animal research and the local ethical committee on animal research of the Radboud University under protocol 2017-0028. All animal experiments were performed according to the institutional guidelines by blinded biotechnicians. Upon arrival, 7–8 weeks old male Sprague Dawley® rats (Envigo, Horst, the Netherlands) were randomly marked with a waterproof marker on their tail for identification and were acclimatized for ≥4 days before any experimental procedure. Rats were randomly allocated to the experimental groups,

assessed daily for welfare and had unlimited access to food and water in a controlled environment (22 ± 1 °C, $55 \pm 10\%$ humidity, 12 h dark/light cycle). Cages were weekly replaced by clean cages.

Multichelated PET study and biodistribution

[⁸⁹Zr]Zr radiolabelled and purified peptides **13** and **18** were adjusted with nonradiolabelled peptide and vehicle to 1 nmol/200 µl. Each animal (n=6 per peptide) was injected with 1 nmol (4-6 MBq) in 200 µl vehicle through an intravenous tail vein injection. At 4 h and 24 h after injection, under general anesthesia or after CO₂ asphyxiation, respectively, animals were imaged for 30 min using an Inveon animal PET scanner (Siemens Preclinical solutions). Reconstruction of scans was performed using Inveon Acquisition Workplace software with an iterative three-dimensional ordered subset expectation maximization using maximum a priori with shifted Poisson distribution algorithm with the following parameters: matrix, 256 × 256 × 161; pixel size, 0.4 × 0.4 × 0.8 mm with a corresponding beta of 0.05 mm. After imaging at 24 h post injection, blood, muscle, lung, spleen, liver, bone marrow, kidney, brain and pancreas were collected for quantification of the radioactive signal using a gamma counter (Wizard, PerkinElmer) and expressed as the percentage of injected dose per gram tissue (%ID/g), calculated from the amount of radioactivity measured in aliquots of the injected dose.

MVK PET study and biodistribution

[⁸⁹Zr]Zr radiolabelled and purified peptide **19** (5 MBq corresponding to 1 nmol) in 200 µl was injected intravenously in the tail vein of rats (n=6). Animals were imaged at 4 h, 8 h, 24 h and 72 h after injection for 15 min, (4 h and 8 h) 20 min (24 h) or 30 min (72 h), using an Inveon animal PET scanner (Siemens Preclinical solutions). Reconstruction of scans was performed using Inveon Acquisition Workplace software with an iterative three-dimensional ordered subset expectation maximization using maximum a priori with shifted Poisson distribution algorithm with the following parameters: matrix, 256 × 256 × 161; pixel size, 0.4 × 0.4 × 0.8 mm with a corresponding beta of 0.05 mm. Animals were euthanized by CO₂ asphyxiation at 24 h (n=3) and 72 h (n=3) after injection and subsequently blood, muscle, lung, spleen, liver, bone marrow, kidney, brain and pancreas were collected for quantification of the radioactive signal using a gamma counter (Wizard, PerkinElmer) and expressed as the percentage of injected dose per gram tissue (%ID/g), calculated from the amount of radioactivity measured in aliquots of the injected dose.

Ancillary Information

Supporting Information

The following results are available in the supplementary information pdf file: GLP-1R potency as EC50 values, Radiolabelling efficiency and molar activity, stability of radiolabelled peptides, statistical analysis of tissue uptake, QWBA biodistribution of [³H]**2**, biodistribution of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-**2**, [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-**13**, [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-**18**, [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-**19** from PET studies, all PET images of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-**13**, [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-**18**, [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-**19**. High resolution mass spectrometry data of all Zr containing peptides and all peptides that were used for radio experiments. QToF or QDa mass spectrometry results are provided for all remaining peptides. UPLC-UV analysis is provided for all peptides.

Description of the following experimental methods is available in the supplementary information: chemicals and reagents, UPLC and LCMS characterization of peptides, concentration determination of peptides, in vitro GLP-1R potency assay, molecular modelling of peptide 18 and zirconium-89 radiolabelling and radio-stability assay and statistical analysis.

Molecular formula SMILES strings for all compounds are supplied as a .csv file.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no potential competing interests.

Author contributions

J.W. designed and synthesized all non-radioactive molecules, contributed to design of radio-labelling and PET studies, compiled and analysed data from all experiments and wrote the manuscript. R.R and M.B designed and performed the radio-labelling experiments, PET study and data analysis. T.G designed and performed in vitro GLP-1R experiments. D.R. generated the 3D model. E.F.A.F contributed to design of PET studies. S.H. and I.B contributed to design of all experiments, data analysis and writing of the manuscript. M.B.F.G contributed to design of molecules, design of all experiments, data analysis and writing of the manuscript. All authors provided critical feedback to the manuscript.

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Abbreviations

A_m: molar activity

BBM: brush border membrane

CNS: central nervous system

DFO: desferrioxamine

EDTA: ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid

FCS: fetal calf serum

GLP-1RA: glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonist

HSA: human serum albumin

iTLC: instant thin-layer chromatography

NEP: neutral endopeptidase

PBS: phosphate buffered saline

PET: positron emission tomography

PK: pharmacokinetics

QWBA: quantitative whole-body autoradiography

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Tables

Table 1. Structure-Activity-Relationship table, GLP-1R potency factor loss vs parent (**1**)

DFO load:	-Zr		+Zr	
	0%	1%	0%	1%
Peptide				
2				1.4*
3	6.3	2.0	3.6	1.3
4	5.8	1.9	3.6	1.2
5	3.9	1.9	3.0	1.8
6	14.2	4.0	4.2	1.9
7	8.4	3.7	3.6	2.0
8	39.5	14.3	57.9	21.4
9	63.2	35.7	68.4	32.1
10	10.5	9.6	28.9	6.4
11	44.7	20.2	5.8	2.6
12	10.0	4.4	4.0	0.8
13	2.9	1.7	1.5	1.2
14	6.8	4.9	11.1	2.3
15	18.9	7.1	10.5	3.6
16	7.4	3.7	2.9	3.3
17	5.3	3.7	6.3	2.3
18	12.1	6.7	3.8	3.1
19	1.5	1.9	1.4	1.2

*data from²⁶

TOC Graphic

Cleavable linker

- Decreased signal from kidneys
- More representative biodistribution

- Increased Am and stability
- Similar receptor activity and biodistribution